

Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding as Presentation of Gastric Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumor: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) are rare mesenchymal neoplasms that account for 1–3% of gastric tumors and arise from the interstitial cells of Cajal. Clinical presentation is variable and may include gastrointestinal bleeding, abdominal pain, anemia, or weight loss. Surgical resection remains the standard treatment for localized disease, requiring accurate clinical, endoscopic, radiologic, and histopathologic evaluation for diagnosis and management.

Case Report: Case report of a 69-year-old man with weight loss, anorexia, and melena caused by a gastric gastrointestinal stromal tumor (GIST). Endoscopy revealed an ulcerated submucosal lesion, while contrast-enhanced CT confirmed a gastric mass without metastases. Endoscopic tattooing and laparoscopic partial gastrectomy were performed. Histopathology confirmed a low-risk GIST (CD117+, DOG1+, negative margins). The patient recovered without complications, was discharged on postoperative day four, and remained recurrence-free at 6 months. This case highlights the importance of multidisciplinary management, imaging-guided laparoscopic surgery, and immunohistochemistry for accurate diagnosis and low-morbidity treatment of gastric GIST presenting as upper gastrointestinal bleeding.

Conclusion: Gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) should be considered in the differential diagnosis of upper gastrointestinal bleeding associated with gastric subepithelial lesions. A multidisciplinary approach, contrast-enhanced computed tomography, endoscopic marking, and laparoscopic resection enable safe and effective treatment of localized low-risk tumors.

KEYWORDS: GIST, Gastrointestinal Bleeding, Laparoscopic Gastrectomy, Stromal Tumor

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
18 June 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) account for approximately 1–3% of gastric neoplasms and originate from the interstitial cells of Cajal, with about 60% arising in the stomach (1). Their clinical presentation is variable and may include gastrointestinal bleeding, abdominal pain, anemia, or weight loss (2).

Diagnosis requires clinical, endoscopic, radiologic, and histopathologic correlation, while surgical resection remains the treatment of choice for localized disease (4,5,10).

II. CASE REPORT

A 69-year-old man with a history of hypothyroidism and benign prostatic growth presented to the emergency department with urinary symptoms and fever. During the clinical interview, he reported anorexia, a 6-kg weight loss, and episodes of melena over the preceding six months.

Initial laboratory studies revealed leukocytosis and findings consistent with a urinary tract infection. Given the history of upper gastrointestinal bleeding, upper endoscopy was performed, revealing an ulcerated submucosal lesion measuring approximately 3 × 2 cm along the greater curvature of the stomach (Fig. 1). Biopsies were obtained, and the lesion was marked with India ink tattooing.

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Figure 1. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy showing an ulcerated submucosal lesion in the upper third of the gastric greater curvature.

Contrast-enhanced computed tomography revealed a 34 × 30 mm gastric mass with both exophytic and endophytic growth patterns, with no evidence of metastatic disease (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Contrast-enhanced abdominal CT demonstrating a hypodense lesion with exophytic and endophytic components arising from the gastric greater curvature.

Laparoscopic partial gastrectomy was performed using a linear stapler. The lesion was successfully identified intraoperatively through the previously placed endoscopic tattoo marking (Fig. 3). The patient had an uneventful postoperative course, resumed oral intake on postoperative day 2, and was discharged on postoperative day 4 without complications.

Figure 3. Endoscopic India ink tattoo marking on the gastric greater curvature identifying the exophytic lesion.

Final histopathology confirmed a 2.9-cm gastrointestinal stromal tumor (GIST) positive for CD117, DOG1, and CD34, with a Ki-67 index of 2%, 3 mitoses per 10 high-power fields, and negative resection margins, consistent with a low-risk tumor.

III. DISCUSSION

Gastric GISTs may present with upper gastrointestinal bleeding secondary to mucosal ulceration, although this presentation is relatively uncommon in small tumors (2,5). Bleeding is typically associated with lesions larger than 5 cm; however, in the present case, a GIST measuring less than 3

cm caused melena and weight loss, highlighting the importance of considering subepithelial lesions in patients with anemia or persistent gastrointestinal bleeding.

Initial endoscopic biopsies may be non-diagnostic because of the tumor's submucosal origin. Therefore, contrast-enhanced computed tomography plays a key role in defining tumor extent and guiding surgical planning (4,6).

GISTs smaller than 5 cm with a low mitotic index are associated with a low risk of malignant progression (5).

Laparoscopic resection with negative margins represents a curative treatment and obviates the need for lymphadenectomy, as lymphatic spread is uncommon in these tumors (4,5).

In addition, preoperative endoscopic tattooing with India ink facilitated intraoperative localization and enabled precise resection, contributing to a favorable postoperative recovery (3,9).

Immunohistochemical positivity for CD117 and DOG1 confirmed the diagnosis of GIST, while the low Ki-67 proliferation index and histopathologic features indicated that adjuvant therapy with imatinib was not required (4,5,7).

IV. CONCLUSION

Gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) should be considered in the differential diagnosis of upper gastrointestinal bleeding associated with gastric subepithelial lesions. A multidisciplinary approach, contrast-enhanced computed tomography, endoscopic marking, and laparoscopic resection enable safe and effective treatment of localized low-risk tumors.

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